

A Rogue Planet as a Trigger for the Late Heavy Bombardment

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We propose that the Late Heavy Bombardment (LHB) may have been triggered by gravitational perturbations from a distant planet following a highly inclined orbit. An undetected planet like we describe could have forced planetesimals from a young disk beyond Neptune into the planetary region, where they would be scattered onto Earth-crossing orbits. We show that this scenario could have occurred on timescales consistent with the Late Heavy Bombardment. We describe the range of planet masses and orbits consistent with observational constraints that validate our model. We conclude that such a planet could be detected by future sky surveys such as the GAIA space mission.

Introduction

Geological data from NASA's Apollo program provide valuable constraints for Solar System evolution models. Most lunar craters are ≈ 3.8 -3.9 billion years old, implying that the moon was blitzed by asteroids and/or comets [1, 2], before impacts tapered off [3].

One class of models for triggering this Late Heavy Bombardment (LHB) begins with a young and tightly packed Solar System. As the orbits of the giant planets expand due to scattering of leftover planetesimals, Jupiter and Saturn cross a mean motion orbital resonance that excites large eccentricities throughout the outer solar system. Once Neptune and Uranus acquire eccentric orbits, they also interact with the planetesimal disk. Such a resonance crossing and planetesimal migration could explain several properties of the current planetary orbits, the orbital distribution of the main-belt asteroids, and the origin of Jupiter's Trojans [4], but other details still need to be refined [5].

Several features of our Solar System remain anomalous [6]. For example, it is not understood how the orbits of some distant Kuiper belt objects (e.g., *Sedna*) could have detached from

the planetary region of the Solar System. Producing these highly inclined and distant bodies seems to require perturbations “from the outside” [7].

A distant, unseen planet could explain several anomalies of our Solar System. For example, Matese et al. (1999) showed that a $3 M_{Jup}$ (Jupiter-mass) planet orbiting at 25,000 AU (Earth is 1 AU from the Sun) could “possibly and perhaps likely” explain an unusually orbiting comet stream [8, 9]. Gomez et al. (2006) found that a M_{Nep} (Neptune-mass) planet within 2000 AU could explain the origin of Sedna-like objects, among other observed anomalies [6]. Lykawka & Mukai (2008) found that much of the Trans-Neptunian architecture could be due to the existence of a small planet, $\approx 0.3\text{-}0.7 M_{\oplus}$ (Earth-mass), between 100-175 AU [10]. Gaudi & Bloom (2005) showed a very broad range of bodies could exist in our Solar System and remain undetected [11].

We propose that an undetected planet could also explain the LHB. In our model, the putative planet would be (or have been) in a highly inclined and likely eccentric orbit, possibly forming around another star and captured by the Sun before the two stars left their star-forming region [12]. Initially, a disk of planetesimals is presumed to have formed with a low-inclination and nearly circular orbit. The putative planet would have triggered the LHB by perturbing planetesimals into high eccentricity orbits that are susceptible to scattering by the giant planets, which ultimately leads to a fraction of the planetesimals bombarding the inner Solar System.

This paper delineates the requirements for a putative planet to trigger the LHB. We present results of two types of numerical integrations to test the viability of our model: 1) octupole-order secular perturbation equations (OSPE) [13] of three-body systems, and 2) direct N -body integrations of the Solar System adding both planetesimals and the putative planet [14]. In § 2, We apply OSPE integrations for a wide variety of planet masses and orbits to identify initial conditions that would result in an LHB-like event, considering only the Sun, a planetesimal and the putative planet. In § 3, we use N -body integrations of a few systems to verify that the qualitative behavior observed in our OSPE simulations is not altered by the perturbations of the known planets. Finally, we discuss the implications of our work (§ 4).

Planet Mass and Orbital Properties

The triggering of the LHB in our model can be understood qualitatively through a three-body model. The secular evolution of hierarchical triple systems are quantitatively described by the OPSE [13]. In this approximation, the semi-major axes are constant, but the eccentricities and inclinations evolve on long timescales. For systems with a relative inclination exceeding 40° , the dynamics is dominated by the quadrupole term (i.e., the “Kozai” regime). In this simplified regime, secular interactions cause large periodic variations of the eccentricity of the inner orbit (e_{in}) which are coupled to variations in the relative inclination (i_{rel}), so as to conserve the z -component of the angular momentum and thus the constant of motion, $(1 - e_{in}^2) \cos^2 i_{rel}$. In this idealized model, the amplitude of the eccentricity variations depends on the initial relative inclination, but not the mass or orbital distance of the outer body, making it possible for a distant

planet to excite large eccentricities. The planet’s mass and orbital distance affect the timescale for the eccentricity variations, and the dynamics can be qualitatively altered if additional effects (e.g., perturbations of other planets) operate on shorter timescales.

To determine whether a putative planet could trigger a LHB-like event by exciting the eccentricities of a planetesimal disk, we simulated an ensemble of hierarchical triple systems, each containing the Sun, a planetesimal ($10^{-9}M_{Sun}$) around 100 AU, and an outer planet initially inclined relative to the orbit of the planetesimal. We use the OSPE to calculate the orbital evolution of the planetesimal due to the gravitational perturbations of the putative planet. Fig. 1 shows how e_{in} evolves with time for various planet properties. Changing the mass (panel a) and distance (panel b) of the perturbing planet affects the timescale of the variations. The larger and closer the perturbing planet, the more volatile the planetesimal’s eccentricity. We find that this model can result in large eccentricities on timescales of 10^8 years, for planet masses and orbits consistent with current constraints [11].

We use this model to estimate the parameters of a planet that could perturb planetesimals onto high eccentricity ($e_{in} \geq 0.6$) orbits on timescales comparable to the LHB (≤ 600 Myr). Fig. 2 shows the range of planet masses and semi-major axes where $\max e_{in} \geq 0.6$. We find that decreasing the outer planet’s inclination to 40° or less nearly eliminates the allowed parameters for a LHB-causing planet, while altering the planet’s eccentricity has a lesser effect. Our OSPE results suggest that a LHB-causing planet could have masses from $0.5 M_{\oplus}$ at 135 AU, to $10^4 M_{\oplus}$ at 5000 AU.

Detailed Orbital Dynamics

In order to further test our model, we performed a collection of 600 Myr N -body simulations using the *Mercury* hybrid symplectic integrator [14] with 100 day time-steps. These simulations include the gravitational perturbations of the putative planet as well as Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. Once planetesimals suffer close encounters with Neptune, their orbits can evolve very differently due to chaos. Most are scattered inwards to the other planets at which point the distant planet is no longer important for their evolution. Fig. 3 shows the percentage of planetesimals that become Jupiter-crossing, for a range of perturbing planets, before the planetesimals are ejected from the system. The N -body integrations suggest that a LHB-causing planet could have masses from $10 M_{\oplus}$ at 200 AU, to $3000 M_{\oplus}$ at 1000 AU.

Discussion

We find a broad range of planet masses and orbits that could trigger an LHB-like event, consistent with observational constraints [11]. A planet in this range would explain other puzzling features of the Solar System [6, 10]. The GAIA sky survey will investigate about 80% of our range for LHB-causing planets, so if a planet like we describe is now in our Solar System, we

predict that it could be detected during the processing of data from the GAIA mission: 2013-2020. If such a planet orbited with a relative inclination exceeding 40° , then it likely caused the LHB. If no such planet is detected, our model may still be a possible explanation of the LHB, since highly inclined bodies can have unstable orbits and be ejected [15].

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Figure captions

- **Figure 1** This figure shows the eccentricity evolution of a planetesimal with a semi-major axis of 100 AU, as perturbed by a putative planet orbiting 60° from the ecliptic with an eccentricity of 0.7. Panel **(a)** simulations are for a planet with semi-major axis of 1000 AU. Line-styles and color distinguish 5 different planet masses tested: $317 M_\oplus$ (*long green dashes*), $158 M_\oplus$ (*magenta line*), $34 M_\oplus$ (*long-short blue dashes*), $17 M_\oplus$ (*short black dashes*), and $3 M_\oplus$ (*red dots*). Panel **(b)** simulations are for a planet mass of $63 M_\oplus$. Line-styles and color distinguish 5 different planet semi-major axes tested: 500 AU (*long green dashes*), 750 AU (*magenta line*); 1000 AU (*long-short blue dashes*); 1500 AU (*short black dashes*); and 2000 AU (*red dots*).
- **Figure 2** This contour plot shows the range of planet masses and semi-major axes where the maximum eccentricity of the inner planet (e_{in}) exceeds 0.6 (green), exceeds 0.3 (yellow), or remains less than 0.3 (red), based on OSPE integrations with $a_{in} = 100$ AU, $e_p = 0.6$, and $i_{rel} = 60^\circ$. The grey region indicates parameters excluded by current observational constraints [11]. Results from an ensemble of N -body integrations are also indicated, by black symbols. Each symbol indicates whether at least one planetesimal's pericenter drops below 5 AU between 300 and 600 Myr for all (*filled circle*), some (*asterisk*) or none (*empty circle*) of the initial conditions considered (e_p from 0.2 to 0.8 and i_{rel} from 40° to 80°).
- **Figure 3** This figure shows the results of N -body integrations for a perturbing planet with a semi-major axis of 400 AU, eccentricity of 0.6 and orbital inclination of 60° from the ecliptic. It shows the percentage of planetesimals whose whose pericenter becomes < 5 AU between 0 and 600 Myr. This percentage is evaluated as a function of time for five planet masses: $3000 M_\oplus$ (*long green dashes*), $1000 M_\oplus$ (*magenta line*), $300 M_\oplus$ (*long-short blue dashes*), $100 M_\oplus$ (*short black dashes*), and $30 M_\oplus$ (*red dots*).

Figure 1

Figure 3

